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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the conductivity and structure of nanocrystalline CaF₂ films grown at 200 °C by thermal evaporation. The in-plane conductivity is enhanced by several orders of magnitude compared to lightly doped bulk samples of CaF₂, which independently confirms the finding of a previous work [Modine *et al.*, J. Appl. Phys. **74**, 2658 (1993)]. Upon heating above 200 °C, the enhancement is partially annealed out, and the activation energy increases continuously from 0.7 to 1.0 eV, which contradicts the annealing model proposed previously. The enhancement is seen only in an ~20-nm thick region adjacent to the substrate, but this may be because the films show substantial porosity outside this region. A 5–10 nm grain size and a high density of grain boundaries are observed by high-resolution transmission electron microscopy. A 2–4 nm interfacial amorphous layer is seen in films grown on Al₂O₃, but such a layer is absent on MgO and evidently not responsible for the enhanced conduction. Overall, the evidence points to grain boundaries and/or dislocations as providing fast transport pathways. These results help to reconcile previous reports of enhanced ion transport in CaF₂, and they are also relevant for understanding the enhancement mechanism in CaF₂-based composites and antifluorite-structured materials such as Li₂O.

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INTRODUCTION

Thin films can exhibit charge transport properties that deviate substantially from bulk samples of the same material. Careful investigation of these situations is useful for revealing new insights into the physics of charge transport at interfaces, grain boundaries, and dislocations. This work focuses on calcium fluoride (CaF₂), which is a useful model material in film studies for several reasons. First, the bulk defect chemistry of CaF₂ is relatively well studied and provides a baseline for understanding differences that arise in films. Second, CaF₂ is stable against humidity and low electron-beam doses, which enables structural characterization by high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM).¹ Third, one might expect that improved transport at interfaces and higher-dimensional defects in ionic materials is most likely when the bulk structure shows poor conductivity, as in CaF₂.² Fourth, CaF₂ is a model compound for the (anti)fluorite crystal structure, so understanding charge transport at defects in CaF₂ films is expected to help explain the behavior of other systems, including films containing antifluorite Li₂O and Li₂S, which are heavily studied for battery applications.^{3–6}

Let us first review the bulk behavior. Calcium fluoride is the archetype of the fluorite structure and is well described by a defect

chemical model based on anti-Frenkel disorder. The conductivity is predominantly due to mobile F[−] ions.⁷ Doping studies on single crystals find a migration enthalpy of 0.5–0.6 eV for F[−] vacancies^{7–12} and 0.9 eV for interstitial F[−] ions.¹³ These defects tend to associate with dopants below about 300–400 °C, which lowers the mobile defect concentration and conductivity while increasing the activation energy. Confusion over association effects led some previous works to suggest higher values for the migration enthalpies,^{7,14,15} as noted previously.¹³ Another complication is that unintended oxygen incorporation and/or surface decomposition in samples heated above 650 °C can increase the conductivity at lower temperatures.⁷ Yet, there is excellent agreement about the intrinsic conductivity at 600–900 °C,^{7,8,10,16,17} and the enthalpy of anti-Frenkel disorder shows a rather high value of 2.4 eV,¹³ which corresponds to weak ionic disorder and low intrinsic defect concentrations. As a result, single crystals of “undoped” CaF₂ show a low ionic conductivity of about 10^{−17} S/cm at 25 °C.⁸ Dissolving dopants in the structure can increase the vacancy concentration and ionic conductivity by several orders of magnitude, up to a limit of about 10^{−11} S/cm at 25 °C.

The structure of evaporated CaF₂ films was investigated in several works, motivated partly by a possible application as a dielectric material in semiconductor devices. Early studies by

transmission electron microscopy (TEM) found that the films grew epitaxially on NaCl(100) substrates and transitioned from polycrystallinity to monocrystallinity when the growth temperature was increased from 150–250 to 350 °C.^{18–20} X-ray rocking curves suggested a similar transition on Si substrates.²¹ On Ge substrates, CaF₂ films were seen by TEM to be porous below 330 °C and dense above 400 °C.²² On glass substrates, CaF₂ films grown at room temperature showed a constant porosity of 46% by atomic force microscopy (AFM) for all thicknesses in the range 50–500 nm.²³ Based on these studies, CaF₂ films grown below ~300 °C can be expected to exhibit small grain sizes and substantial porosity.

The charge transport behavior in CaF₂ films has also been investigated. After evaporation onto Al₂O₃ at 500 °C, films showed a macroscopic in-plane conductivity σ_m with a similar magnitude (within a factor of 3) and activation energy (1.1 eV for $\sigma_m T$) as that of nominally undoped single crystals (0.9–1.1 eV in the extrinsic regime at 350–500 °C).²⁴ Independent measurements of the through-plane conductivity after evaporation onto Al₂O₃ at 200 °C showed a similar magnitude (6×10^{-10} S cm⁻¹ at 200 °C) and activation energy (1.0 eV).²⁵ Evaporation onto SiO₂ led to a similar in-plane conductivity (within a factor of 2).¹⁴ (As a note, the activation energies appear to be miscalculated in Ref. 14.) Evaporation onto Si at 600 °C yielded a low through-plane conductivity of 5×10^{-15} S cm⁻¹ at 25 °C.²⁶ Sputter-deposited CaF₂ films on Pt-coated Al₂O₃ showed a similar through-plane conductivity.²⁷ A few earlier works observed hysteresis in electrical measurements with a sweeping voltage, which likely reflects the fact that ions are the predominant mobile charge carriers (see Ref. 28, and references cited therein). Broadly speaking, all these film measurements are consistent with the behavior of lightly doped bulk CaF₂, with interstitial F⁻ ions as the dominant charge carriers.

By contrast, substantially higher in-plane conductivities were reported in Ref. 25. In that work, evaporation onto Al₂O₃ at 200 °C led to an in-plane conductivity that was enhanced by several orders of magnitude compared to that of bulk CaF₂, but only in the first ~10 nm of the film. Co-evaporation of CaF₂ and Al₂O₃ yielded a similar enhancement in the first ~10 nm, as well as a more modest enhancement in the next 800 nm of growth. Adding a capping layer of Al₂O₃ on an ~14 nm CaF₂ film yielded no change in conductivity. These findings were attributed to fast transport of F⁻ ions along dislocations in CaF₂ near Al₂O₃ interfaces. However, the possible roles of grain boundaries and porosity were not discussed. Moreover, no enhancement was seen for the CaF₂ films in two subsequent works,^{14,24} despite the fact that those works used the same substrate (α -Al₂O₃) and a growth temperature that was only modestly higher (~500 °C). Considering these points, it is worth investigating whether the results and interpretation in Ref. 25 are accurate. This work presents that investigation with a focus on in-plane transport measurements, which are a standard method for probing interfacial effects in films^{24,29,30} while avoiding problems with short circuiting that can arise in a through-plane geometry.²⁷

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Single crystal α -Al₂O₃ (0001) and MgO (100) substrates (Crystec GmbH, 10 × 10 × 0.5 mm, one side polished) were placed in a box furnace designated for “clean” materials and pre-annealed

at 600 °C in ambient air for 6 h. For a few Al₂O₃ samples, the pre-anneal was performed at 1300 °C. The substrates were then installed in a vacuum chamber (Createc, base pressure of 10⁻¹⁰ mbar) and heated from the backside to 200 °C using a resistive heater. The heater temperature was measured by a nearby thermocouple, and the temperature difference between that thermocouple and the substrate surface was calibrated in advance using a pyrometer and a substrate with known emissivity. Films were grown by evaporation of CaF₂ (Alfa, 99.95%) onto the polished side of the substrate from an alumina crucible at 1300–1330 °C. The substrate and the CaF₂ source were allowed to reach thermal equilibrium before the shutters were opened to begin growth. Various growth times in the range 560–9000 s were used, depending on the evaporation flux and the desired film thickness. A quartz crystal thickness monitor located near the sample holder showed that the evaporation flux remained steady during any given growth, but it decreased slowly over several weeks due to slow accumulation of CaF₂ at the crucible aperture. After growth, each sample was cooled to 25 °C and transferred without air exposure to an argon-filled glove box (MBraun).

For transport measurements, films were contacted by 60–500 nm thick ruthenium electrodes (Lesker 99.95%) applied by DC sputtering (Emitech K575X) through an interdigitated shadow mask. The electrode samples were pressed against platinum wires in a quartz holder, installed in a quartz tube inside a tube furnace, and heated under 50 sccm (~10 cm/s) argon flow to various temperatures in the range 25–400 °C as measured by a thermocouple adjacent to the substrate. Typically, a 0.5 h dwell was employed at each temperature to reach equilibrium. Impedance spectra were acquired using a frequency analyzer (Novocontrol Alpha-A) over the range 10⁰–10⁻² Hz. At room temperature, each spectrum corresponded to a perfect capacitor. Above about 80 °C, each spectrum formed an arc or full semicircle that was fit by a parallel R-CPE equivalent circuit (Zview). The resistance R was converted to conductivity using the standard relation $\sigma = L/(RA)$, where L is the 0.5 mm spacing between the electrodes and A is the cross-sectional area, which equals film thickness × 7.5 cm for the interdigitated electrode geometry in this work. The effective capacitance (calculated from $C_{\text{eff}} = Q^n R^{n-1}$, where Q and n are the magnitude and exponent of the constant phase element) is 5 pF in all spectra, consistent with stray capacitance from the substrate. Above about 180 °C, a second arc appears in the spectra at low frequencies; this arc is evidence of ion-blocking behavior at the electrodes and is otherwise neglected. For a few samples, DC polarization and depolarization measurements were performed by applying a constant current using a sourcemeter (Keithley 6430).

For the preparation of cross-sectional samples for transmission electron microscopy (TEM), a sandwich was formed using G1 epoxy (Gatan) with a hardening step at 140 °C. The sandwich was then mounted on a holder for tripod polishing (Allied Multiprep) using QuickWax at 150 °C. After tripod polishing, the cross-sectional samples were ion-milled in three steps using 3.3, 2.0, and 0.35 keV Ar⁺ ions at an angle of 8° at liquid N₂ temperature (-196 °C). The final TEM specimen was attached to a Mo grid using MBOND610 (ME Messsysteme) at 150 °C. TEM characterization was performed in a JEOL ARM200F microscope (aberration-corrected objective lens, cold FEG, 200 kV). HRTEM images were

recorded using a Gatan UltraScan 1000XP CCD camera. Irradiation damage was observed (both in the substrate and in the CaF_2 layer) but only after exposure times well exceeding those used for HRTEM imaging in this work. High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) images were acquired using electron scattering angles between 100 and 270 mrad. Electron energy-loss spectra (EELS) were also acquired (110 mrad collection angle, 20.4 mrad illumination angle). EELS linescan measurements required a higher electron dose and dose rate than that used for HRTEM imaging, and damage was occasionally observed after finishing a linescan. The linescan data shown in this work are from measurements where the damage was weak or not observed, but a minor influence of electron-beam-induced damage on the EELS data cannot be fully excluded. A JEOL x-ray detector was used for energy-dispersive x-ray analysis. Data were analyzed using the Pathfinder software (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Film thicknesses were measured using a stylus profilometer (Veeco Dektak 8), or in a few cases by TEM. A grazing incidence x-ray diffraction pattern (Panalytical Empyrean, $\text{Cu K}\alpha$, 2° incident angle) acquired from a 220 nm film showed reflections corresponding to polycrystalline CaF_2 (Fig. S1 in the supplementary material). Atomic force microscopy (Bruker Dimension Icon, PeakForce tapping mode) images were acquired from the substrate surfaces and processed using the Gwyddion software. Literature data were extracted using the WebPlotDigitizer software.³¹

RESULTS

Films grown by CaF_2 evaporation onto $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ substrates at 200°C show a macroscopic in-plane conductivity σ_m that is strongly enhanced relative to lightly doped CaF_2 single crystals. A representative example is shown in Fig. 1; the as-grown enhancement relative to a 0.1% NaF-doped CaF_2 single crystal is 4 orders of magnitude at 80°C . Successive anneals in the range $200\text{--}340^\circ\text{C}$ lead to successive drops in conductivity. After each anneal, the temperature dependence remains essentially stable until the film is exposed to a new higher temperature. For the film in Fig. 1, the activation energies are 0.71 eV as grown, 0.91 eV after a 285°C anneal, and 1.02 eV after a 335°C anneal. These values were reproduced in multiple films. Depending on the extent of annealing, the activation energy could be adjusted to any value in the range 0.7–1.0 eV. Reliable measurements above 340°C were often precluded by coarsening and delamination of the Ru electrodes, but in samples where the electrodes remained intact, heating above 340°C appeared to have little or no further impact on the conductivity.

Figure 2 shows the impact of film thickness. The in-plane resistance measured before and after annealing is approximately the same (within a factor of 2) for several CaF_2 films grown with various thicknesses in the range 17–790 nm. Pre-annealing the Al_2O_3 substrate at 1300°C to produce a terraced substrate surface (Fig. S2 in the supplementary material) has negligible effect on the film resistance. Switching to an $\text{MgO}(100)$ substrate also has negligible effect on the film resistance (Fig. 2). An Al_2O_3 substrate with no film shows a far higher resistance.

To explore the annealing behavior further, the conductance of an as-grown film was measured during a long (26 h) anneal at 200°C . The temperature was then increased to 250°C , and a

FIG. 1. Macroscopic in-plane conductivity of a 17 nm film grown by CaF_2 evaporation onto an $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ substrate at 200°C . Data are shown for the film as grown (blue) and after successive anneals at 285°C (1 h, green) and 335°C (6 h, orange). Colored lines are linear fits. Also shown are reference data from CaF_2 single crystals that were nominally undoped (dark gray), positively doped (0.01 mol. % YF_3 , gray), or negatively doped (0.1 mol. % NaF, light gray).^{8,13}

second long (46 h) anneal was performed. The conductance data collected during these anneals are well fit by lines corresponding to a logarithmic dependence on time [Fig. 3(a)]. After the anneals, the temperature was lowered back to 200°C , and the conductance was found to be essentially stable by AC measurements (drift below 0.2%/h, not shown). Taking advantage of this stable baseline, DC polarization and depolarization measurements were conducted [Fig. 3(b)]. The observed slow relaxation is consistent with ion blocking and accumulation at the metal electrodes, which helps to confirm that the conduction is due to mobile ions, not electrons.

Turning to the microscopy results, Fig. 4 shows the “as-grown” structure of a 220-nm thick film evaporated onto Al_2O_3 at 200°C . HRTEM imaging [Fig. 4(a)] reveals the presence of a 3–4 nm thick amorphous layer at the substrate–film interface. The amorphous layer has a uniform thickness and did not change during observation, which confirms that it is not a result of electron irradiation. Above the amorphous layer, the CaF_2 film is nanocrystalline with a 5–8 nm grain size. Some of the grains are oriented with $\{111\}$ planes approximately parallel to the substrate surface, which suggests that the growth has a preferred orientation. In HAADF images [Figs. 4(b) and 4(c)], the boundary between the amorphous layer and the crystalline CaF_2 is clearly visible as an abrupt transition from dark to bright contrast. The bright contrast is uniform only in the $\sim 20\text{-nm}$ thick crystalline region adjacent to the amorphous layer. The remainder of the film shows speckled

FIG. 2. In-plane resistance of CaF_2 films with various thicknesses before and after heating to 285°C . A control measurement from a bare Al_2O_3 substrate is also shown. All substrates were pre-annealed at 600°C , except the substrate for the 17 nm film was pre-annealed at 1300°C .

contrast, which indicates substantial porosity. The growth exhibits columnar character, in the sense that some pores and grains (or aggregates of grains) are aligned approximately orthogonal to the substrate. Bright-field imaging [Fig. 4(d)] suggests that there is porosity even in the first ~ 20 -nm thick region of the film. An EELS linescan (Fig. S3 in the supplementary material) indicates that the

carbonaceous liquid epoxy used in TEM sample preparation infiltrated most of the film in Fig. 4 but stopped ~ 30 nm from the substrate. The percolation threshold for porosity is roughly 30%,³² which suggests that the porosity in most of the film exceeds this value. Below the amorphous layer, there is a 5–10 nm thick region of the Al_2O_3 substrate, which shows fairly dark contrast in HAADF and bright-field images. This region still shows lattice fringes corresponding to single crystal Al_2O_3 , so the dark contrast in this region is attributed to reduced electron channeling arising from roughness and F accumulation (discussed below) at the Al_2O_3 surface.

By reducing the aperture size of the evaporation source, another film was evaporated at a substantially slower rate (0.15 nm/min) than was used for the film in Fig. 4 (6.6 nm/min). Similar grain size and interfacial structure were observed (Fig. S4 in the supplementary material), suggesting that the film structure is insensitive to the growth rate.

Two other films are shown below. Figure 5(a) shows the film structure after annealing at 340°C . The grain size and orientations appear unaffected by the anneal, and an amorphous interfacial layer is still present, albeit with a slightly reduced thickness of 1–2 nm. Figure 5(b) shows a film grown on an $\text{MgO}(100)$ substrate. The grain size and the structure of the film on MgO are like those of the films on $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$, but there is no amorphous layer at the CaF_2 – MgO interface. The two film specimens in Fig. 5, which have thicknesses of 17 and 28 nm, showed nearly identical transport behavior (Fig. 2) but only one of them contains an amorphous interfacial layer, which is strong evidence that the amorphous layer is not the origin of the enhanced conductivity.

EELS linescans suggest that the amorphous layer on Al_2O_3 substrates contains a mixture of Al, O, F, and perhaps some Ca (Fig. S5 in the supplementary material). Below the amorphous layer, some amount of F extends into the Al_2O_3 substrate, consistent with intermixing and/or adsorption at the substrate surface. Above the amorphous layer, the film reaches a stable Ca:F ratio of approximately 1:2, as expected. Similar results were obtained from multiple regions of each sample and were independent of whether

FIG. 3. (a) Macroscopic in-plane conductance during anneals first at 200°C and then at 250°C . Lines are guides for the eye. (b) DC polarization/depolarization measurements conducted after finishing the anneals in (a) and returning to 200°C .

FIG. 4. Microscopy characterization of the “as-grown” structure of a 220-nm thick CaF_2 film evaporated onto $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ at 200 °C. (a) HRTEM. (b) and (c) HAADF. (d) Bright-field TEM. The position of the interfacial amorphous layer is indicated by dashed lines.

the electron probe was scanned from the Al_2O_3 toward the CaF_2 or vice versa. Energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDX) linescans yielded similar results. For the film grown on $\text{MgO}(100)$, the EELS signal intensities were difficult to quantify due to the overlap of the absorption edges, but the presence or absence of the elements could still be determined. The results tentatively suggest some degree of Ca enrichment at the MgO interface (Fig. S6 in the [supplementary material](#)). At both the Al_2O_3 -amorphous and MgO - CaF_2 interfaces, the oxygen K edge spectra show some

pre-edge intensity at ~ 524 eV (Fig. S7 in the [supplementary material](#)). Such pre-edge intensity is often associated with electronic hole character,³³ but two pieces of evidence suggest that this character has a negligible effect on the measured conduction. First, the metal electrodes block the mobile species [Fig. 3(b)], which speaks for mobile ions rather than electrons. Second, *in situ* measurements show enhanced conductance in at least the first 5–10 nm of the film,²⁵ whereas the pre-edge intensity is somewhat more localized.

FIG. 5. HRTEM images acquired from films grown by CaF_2 evaporation onto (a) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ and (b) $\text{MgO}(100)$ substrates. Prior to TEM specimen preparation, these films were characterized by electrical measurements that involved annealing up to (a) 340 °C for 6 h or (b) 285 °C for 1 h, as shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

DISCUSSION

This work independently reproduced several interesting results from Ref. 25 related to the conductance of evaporated CaF_2 films. The in-plane ionic conductivity is strongly enhanced, and the magnitude observed *ex situ* in this work shows reasonable agreement (within a factor of 3) to that seen *in situ* in Ref. 25 (Fig. 6). The as-grown activation energy of 0.71 eV is close to the range 0.6 ± 0.1 eV reported in Ref. 25, and that work suggested that the range it gave may be a bit low due to imperfect temperature calibration. Both works show that essentially all the conductance arises from a region within 20 nm of the film–substrate interface, and both works find that, upon annealing, the conductance decays with a $\log(\text{time})$ dependence.

This work also showed that CaF_2 films evaporated at 200 °C are nanocrystalline and exhibit substantial porosity (probably >30% in most regions), in agreement with the previous structural studies reviewed in the introduction. The porosity is reduced only within an ~20-nm thick region adjacent to the substrate. Considering this point, one can reasonably wonder whether the fast transport is localized near the interface only because porosity prevents the fast pathways from percolating in the rest of the film. A useful experiment to test this possibility would be to evaporate a thick film, scrape off the porous material, press it into a dense compact to minimize the porosity, and measure the conductivity.

In fact, that experiment has already been reported,³⁴ based on an earlier work.³⁵ Pressed compacts of CaF_2 powder prepared by inert gas condensation (~9 nm grain size) exhibited a conductivity that matches the film conductivity in this work within a factor of 2 (Fig. 6), and the conductivity of the compacts decreased upon annealing above 230 °C or above. The excellent agreement indicates that the same conduction mechanism is present in Refs. 25, 34, and

FIG. 6. Macroscopic conductivity data reported for CaF_2 films,^{14,24,25,27} CaF_2 nanopowders,^{34,36} CaF_2 bulk samples,^{8,13} and CaF_2 - Al_2O_3 composites.^{37–39} For films, the caption indicates whether the conductivity was measured in-plane (||) or through-plane (⊥).

this work. Yet, the powder compacts in Ref. 34 were far thicker than the films in this work. The precise dimensions of the compacts were not given, but one can reasonably assume that only a minuscule fraction of each compact came from the first ~20 nm of the deposit. Thus, the results of Ref. 34 support the hypothesis that the apparent localization of fast transport within 20 nm of the CaF_2 -substrate interface is an artifact arising from porosity.

Let us now discuss the enhancement mechanism. The as-grown film conductivity is far too high to be explained by simple doping of bulk-like CaF_2 . In particular, to achieve in bulk CaF_2 the conductivity of $5 \times 10^{-9} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ exhibited by the as-grown films at 80 °C, a dopant concentration well above 10 mol. % would be required. There is no reason to expect such a high doping level, and it was not detected in EELS or EDX linescans. Also, the dissociation of defect pairs in negatively doped bulk CaF_2 leads to a reversible change in activation energy starting around 250 °C (e.g., the line in Fig. 1 corresponding to a 0.1 mol. % NaF-doped bulk sample starts to bend). This behavior is absent in the annealed CaF_2 films. It is also highly unlikely that the enhanced conductivity is due to a change in fluorine activity, because the ionic defect concentrations and conductivity in CaF_2 are essentially constant over a wide range of fluorine activity due to the predominant ionic disorder.^{40,41} (See Figs. 4–8 in Ref. 42 for an analogous theoretical discussion.) In short, the film behavior observed in this work is inconsistent with bulk-like transport in CaF_2 considering only point defects.

Strain effects at the substrate interface are unlikely to be responsible for the enhancement, because the conductivity is independent of substrate, and for the films grown on Al_2O_3 , the amorphous layer should allow efficient strain relaxation. The amorphous layer likely arises due to the reaction of CaF_2 with adsorbed species such as hydroxides, which can remain on Al_2O_3 even after a 1300 °C anneal.⁴³ By contrast, pre-annealing MgO at 700 °C under vacuum temporarily removes virtually all adsorbates,⁴⁴ and a similar pre-anneal (600 °C) was implemented in this work. In any case, the amorphous layer itself is unlikely to account for the enhanced conductivity, as discussed above.

An important clue discovered in the present work is that the activation energy of σT can take any value in the range 0.7–1.0 eV, depending on the extent of annealing. [An increase in the activation energy upon annealing CaF_2 nanopowder was also observed in an early nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) study.⁴⁵] This finding rules out the dislocation annealing model proposed in Ref. 25, because in that model, the conductance decays only due to a decrease in the number of dislocations, while the activation energy remains constant. Another clue is that annealing at 340 °C substantially reduces the film conductivity but leaves the grain size largely unaffected. Also, nanocrystalline powders investigated in two works^{34,36} showed virtually identical average grain sizes (9 and 10 nm) and activation energies (both 0.8 eV), but the measured conductivities in those works differed by over two orders of magnitude (Fig. 6). Evidently, the conductivity enhancement depends on more than just the number density of grain boundaries.

One possible explanation is that interstitial F^- conduction is enhanced along grain boundaries and/or dislocations due to a higher mobility. The change in activation energy upon annealing could reflect strain relaxation near the defects or a change in the

core structure. The defect cores have a width of <1 nm, so they are unlikely to percolate in the porous regions of the films, which could explain why the through-plane conductivity appeared bulk-like in Refs. 25 and 27. Due to the nanocrystalline structure, we are unable to directly confirm the presence or absence of dislocations, but in principle, misfit dislocations may be present between adjacent CaF_2 nanocrystals when the misorientation angle is small.^{33,46}

Another plausible explanation is that space-charge zones with higher conductivity arise adjacent to CaF_2 grain boundaries and/or dislocations, with a segregation enthalpy that changes as a function of annealing and preparation method. In a simple space-charge model, the activation energy for conduction approximately equals the migration enthalpy plus half the segregation enthalpy.⁴⁷ By this model, in order for the activation energy of the as-grown films (0.7 eV) to equal the F^- vacancy mobility (0.5–0.6 eV) plus half the segregation enthalpy, the latter would need to be 0.2–0.4 eV. A similar calculation for the annealed films (1.0 eV) implies a segregation enthalpy of 1.0 eV. Thus, the segregation enthalpy would need to increase from 0.2–0.4 to 1.0 eV upon annealing at 340 °C, which is substantial but not implausible. A discrepancy in this explanation is that one would expect the through-plane film conductivity to also be somewhat enhanced, since the space-charge zones should percolate along the columnar aggregates of ~ 10 nm grains. Instead, the through-plane conductivity is bulk-like in both evaporated^{25,26} and sputtered²⁷ CaF_2 films. This explanation also implies that a ~ 1.0 eV activation energy can arise in CaF_2 films from two different mechanisms—bulk-like interstitial migration in microcrystalline films^{14,24} or vacancy migration along space-charge zones in nanocrystalline films—which is a somewhat unlikely coincidence.

Both of the above explanations are consistent with previous reports of fast transport at CaF_2 grain boundaries,^{34,36,48} and both offer plausible explanations for the difference in conductivity between differently prepared nanocrystalline samples.^{34,36} The increase in growth temperature from 200 to 500 °C is sufficient to explain the difference in grain size and ion transport between Ref. 25 (plus this work) and Refs. 14 and 24, so, in fact, there is no discrepancy between these works. It is also noteworthy that LiI ,⁴⁹ Li_2O ,⁵⁰ and Li_2S ⁵⁰ films show similar Li^+ transport behavior as seen for F^- transport in this work, which is additional strong evidence for a common enhancement mechanism based on structural defects rather than a specific chemical composition.

A few final comments are worth making about sintered CaF_2 - Al_2O_3 composites. Enhanced F^- conductivity at the two-phase interfaces in such composites has been convincingly demonstrated with reasonable agreement in five works.^{37–39,51,52} One work used α - Al_2O_3 directly,⁵² and two other works sintered at 1300 °C³⁷ and 1227 °C,³⁸ temperatures at which other phases of Al_2O_3 are expected to convert to the α - Al_2O_3 phase,^{53,54} which is also the phase of the substrates in this work. We are thus confronted with the fact that CaF_2 in contact with α - Al_2O_3 shows enhanced conductivity when prepared at ≤ 200 °C as a nanocrystalline film or powder (Refs. 25 and 34 and this work) or at ≥ 1200 °C as a sintered nanocomposite^{37–39,51,52} but not at ~ 500 °C as a microcrystalline film.^{14,24} Furthermore, the conductivity of composites sintered at high temperature shows a similar activation energy (0.63–0.69 eV)^{37–39} as that of our as-grown films (0.71 eV), and if the as-grown conductivity is extrapolated to higher temperatures, the

magnitude is only a factor of ~ 5 higher than that of the best composites³⁷ (Fig. 6). Despite this agreement, the enhancement mechanism in composites sintered at high temperatures could be distinct from the present work and involve interfacial interdiffusion (e.g., O incorporation into the CaF_2), which enhances the fluoride vacancy concentration. Related evidence for such interdiffusion was seen in annealing studies of the CeO_2 - CaF_2 interface.⁵⁵

CONCLUSION

This work independently confirms that F^- conduction is strongly enhanced in nanocrystalline CaF_2 films grown at 200 °C. The enhancement is independent of the substrate structure and composition. It appears to arise only within an ~ 20 -nm thick region nearest the substrate, but the underlying reason may be that the films exhibit substantial porosity outside of this region. The enhancement is partially annealed out by heating above the growth temperature, and the activation energy increases steadily from 0.7 to 1.0 eV depending on the extent of annealing, which offers important clues about the mechanism. This work includes the first HRTEM investigation of a halide-insulator interface exhibiting enhanced ion transport. A 2–4 nm interfacial amorphous layer is observed in films grown on Al_2O_3 but this layer is absent on MgO , and it appears to not be the origin of the enhanced conduction. Instead, the combined evidence in this work and previous works points to fast F^- transport along grain boundaries and/or dislocations in CaF_2 .

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

See the [supplementary material](#) for additional HRTEM, XRD, and AFM data.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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